

UDC 027.7(477): 002.2(474.5) «18/20»

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Lithuania in the University Library's Book Collection

The objective of this article is to examine the book collection related to the history, geography, and culture of Lithuania, stored in the university library's holdings, categorized by fields of knowledge, content, author groups, chronological boundaries, and printing design. **Methods.** The research focused on book publications from the 19th to the early 20th centuries, sourced from various departments of the scientific library. The methodology involved studying both world and Ukrainian historical and literary heritage, employing research methods such as analytical-synthetic, system-structural, comparative, and statistical approaches. **Results.** The findings indicate that this collection serves as a valuable resource for studying the country's history, especially the history of Lithuania and the Lithuanian people from ancient times to the early 20th century. The library's collection revealed significant copies valuable for their content and printing characteristics, and helped identify key aspects of Lithuania's historical, geographical, and cultural development. Particular attention was given to author groups and publisher seals on the publications. **Conclusions.** In today's context, studying global book heritage remains a relevant and vital aspect of library work. The collection on the history, geography, and culture of Lithuania provides a solid foundation for understanding the origins and evolution of Ukrainian-Lithuanian relations. Rare documents are an essential part of providing a quality educational experience for university students.

Keywords: book collections of the 19th – 20th centuries; Lithuania; university library

Introduction

The identity of a scientific library is defined by its core values, including its book collections. The library's fund is a system that contains data providing information about the library's significance. Using research tools, one library collaborates with others to study global and Ukrainian heritage history. The Russian-Ukrainian war of 2022 changed the cultural priorities of the Baltic countries. At book fairs in Vilnius, interest in Ukraine, its diverse publishing market, and contemporary Ukrainian literature is increasing (Drapak, 2023). Meanwhile, Ukrainian scholars are drawn to studying book collections related to Lithuania's history, geography, and culture, stored in Ukrainian libraries, and to sharing information with a diverse readership. This research focuses on searching, selecting, and processing sources and literature from the 19th and early 20th centuries concerning Lithuania's state formation, ethnography, and language issues, stored in the collections of the scientific library at Oles Honchar Dnipro National University (DNU).

Methods

In accordance with the tasks set, the research employed analytical-synthetic, system-structural, comparative, and statistical methods of scientific research. Using this methodology, a systematic historical, book, and library research was conducted. The documentary resources of the university library were analysed and categorized by subject, content, authorship, editorial boards, chronology, language features, external and internal publishing design, seals, and donation inscriptions.

Results and Discussions

The Scientific Library of Oles Honchar DNU features multidisciplinary, multilingual, and holistic thematic collections that receive continual attention from scholars. Of particular interest are individual copies of important books from the 16th to early 20th centuries, which are kept in the department of rare and valuable publications. Within the university's diverse book collection, a noteworthy subset is dedicated to and historically linked with Lithuania and the Baltic countries. Based on our estimates, this historical and geographical collection includes about 100 copies of multidisciplinary publications in various languages from the 19th and 20th centuries.

Conventionally, the collection can be divided into three categories: historical and geographical works by notable scientists; legislative documents such as laws and statutes; and individual works focused on the Grand Duchy of Lithuania and its connections with Ukraine. Analysing the collection by content helps identify reference materials, along with scientific, educational, and popular books. The largest portion consists of historical and geographical works and ethnographic essays by well-known teachers and scientists from the 19th and early 20th centuries. (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Quantitative collection indicators

Worthy of attention are the extensive reference publications of German scientists, professors G. Helmholtz and R. Mayr ("History of Humanity. Vol. 6. 1904"), as well as professors of literature and history at the University of Paris, E. Lavisse and A. Rambaud ("General History from the 4th Century to Our Time. Vol. 1, Vol. 2. 1897"). The first mentions of the ancient Lithuanian settlements as a separate ethnographic group appear in the first and second volumes of the translated edition. The rare edition department houses a significant multi-volume work, "Materials for the Geography and Statistics of Russia" (1861), compiled by D. Afanasiev, an employee of the Imperial Geographical Society. The eleventh volume offers a detailed description of the history and geography of the Kovenska province (within the boundaries of the modern city of Kaunas). This scientific publication comprises eight chapters, thoroughly covering all aspects of the province's development. Chapter VIII describes 15 cities and towns, with the main being the provincial and county seat of Kovno (Kaunas) (Afanasiev, 1861). (Figure 2).

Fig. 2.

Kyiv edition of the beginning of the First World War by the Ukrainian historian and archivist from the early twentieth century, P. V. Klymenko, is valuable for the location of the printing house (Imperial University of St. Volodymyr, now T. H. Shevchenko Kyiv National University) and the materials stored in the manuscript department of the Public Library of Vilno (present-day Vilnius) about the history and life of artisans in Vilno during the 17th century. It also includes the results of the Vilenska Archeographic Commission (1864-1914). The publication received a gold medal as an award. Notably, Professor of History M. V. Dovnar-Zapolskyi, who defended his dissertation on the history of the Grand Duchy of Lithuania, initiated the publication. This comprehensive publication features separate sections that focus on craft guilds, monetary relations, and financial issues. The author highlights that the 17th century was a period of significant development for the craft industry, encompassing social organization, political and legal systems, and religious rituals. The pages clearly show the historical connection between Lithuanians and Germans during the 17th and 18th centuries. The publication is well-sourced, with references. Interesting appendices include vilenski statutes and samples of trial works from craft workshops in Vilno. The bibliography lists 34 sources, primarily German-language works and writings by prominent Ukrainian historians from the 19th to early 20th centuries, such as M. Hrushevskyi and O. Kistiakivskyi (Klymenko, 1914). (Figure 3).

Fig. 3.

The collection includes notable educational literature from the late 19th and early 20th centuries. In particular, it features the Warsaw edition of the renowned Ukrainian historian, rector of Novorosiisk (Odesa) University, and professor of history at the University of Warsaw (1892-1902), F. I. Leontovych. His work on the history of the peasantry, nobility, and territorial organization of the lands of the Grand Duchy of Lithuania (1897) draws attention. This publication belongs to the educational literature prepared with the support of the Council of the Imperial Warsaw University and contains extensive references and explanations that are particularly valuable. Also notable are the world history textbooks by the esteemed teacher, geographer, and prolific author M. I. Zuiev. In one of his early textbooks, he dedicated a section to the Grand Duchy of Lithuania, recounting its history during the 14th and 15th centuries (1852). The book's significance lies in its publication after the censorship of 1851 and its seal, which indicates its belonging to the library of the Katerynoslav Provincial Gymnasium (Zuiev, 1954). (Figure 4).

Fig. 4.

In 1908, four issues of the school publication "Stories from the History of the Western Outskirts of Russia" were published. The first and third issues thoroughly and comprehensively cover history, culture, and various religious denominations, whose representatives include missionaries (10th - early 11th centuries), Lithuanian princes (12th - 13th centuries), and the 19th century. The presentation of material about the cities of Vilno, Revel, and Yuriv is particularly interesting. The publications feature black-and-white illustrations that visually complement the text. A complete bibliography has been compiled for the chapters. The publication from the early twentieth century aims to foster a religious worldview in children.

The textbooks from the collection of selected topics should include a small-format and volume geographical publication from the early 20th century. "Stories about Lithuania and Lithuanians" is recommended for libraries of lower educational institutions and public reading rooms. The preface reveals the clear goal and basis for preparing this publication. Each of the 13 chapters covers the history of Vilno, trade and transport routes, daily life and peasantry, family customs and marriage, economic and craft development, and calendar holidays. The educational content is presented in a popular and accessible manner. Lithuanian legends are particularly interesting. Illustrations accompany each chapter meaningfully. Among the historical and geographical works, the ethnographic essay "Baltic Region" (1901) is noteworthy. This small-volume book was published in the "Public Books" series under the editorship of

O. A. Ivanovskiy, an anthropologist, geographer, and professor at Kharkiv University. In the late 19th century, he was known for essays on local history. The publication mentions the Dnieper and Western Dvina rivers, local lakes, and describes the climate and marine scenes, supported by photographs (Bakirov, Dukhopelnykov, & Zaitsev, 2004).

This collection highlights important legislative documents, including the Law Code of 1468 and the Lithuanian Statutes of 1529, 1566, and 1588. The Law Code of Casimir from 1468 is the earliest compilation of legal norms and judicial procedures of the Grand Duchy of Lithuania, regarded as a law textbook. This historical document was in force across most Ukrainian lands that were part of the Grand Duchy. In 1967, the Lithuanian SSR Academy of Sciences published an edition edited by A. Tila, featuring the text of the Law Code, its Lithuanian translation, and explanations by Professor A. Yanulaitys. This work serves as a valuable source of 15th-century legal terminology. The document, comprising 25 points, was drafted under Grand Duke Casimir IV Jagiellon. Also noteworthy is the research by Ukrainian lawyer, statesman, and public figure Andrii Ivanovych Yakovliv, a professor at the Ukrainian University in Prague. His 1929 diaspora edition, printed in Prague, examines the influence of Old Czech law on Ukrainian legal development in the 15th–16th centuries. This edition also discusses three Lithuanian Statutes (1529, 1566, 1588) as legal sources and includes a collection of legal cases. It provides insight into language issues of the 15th–16th centuries, especially the use of Czech terms in Lithuanian documents. The conclusions are written in both Ukrainian and Lithuanian. The coat of arms of the Ukrainian University in Prague, displayed on the back of the title page, draws attention (Rymarenko et al., 1996). (Figure 5).

Fig. 5.

The collection includes a valuable academic edition from 1960, titled “Statute of the Grand Duchy of Lithuania in 1529,” edited by K. I. Yablonskis, a 20th-century Lithuanian historian and professor at Vilnius University. The foreword was written by the renowned historian, educator, and member of the Katerynoslav Scientific Archival Commission, V. I. Picheta. The edition features the main text and translation across 13 chapters, along with a user-friendly alphabetical dictionary-commentary. Among the sources in this group, it is notable that the edition includes a reprint version of the teaching and methodological manual by the Lithuanian historian S. A. Lazutka, from the early 20th to the early 21st century, prepared at Vilnius University for history students studying Lithuanian historiography during the feudal period. Lazutka studied the first Statute of the Grand Duchy of Lithuania from 1529, explored the context and reasons for its creation, and analysed its importance in the legal confirmation of

feudal relations. He also prepared an authoritative text of the statute based on all existing 16th-century texts. The publication is illustrated with colour photographs from the original First Lithuanian Statute (Panova-Striuk, 2009). (Figure 6).

Fig. 6.

The history of Lithuania has long intrigued Ukrainian historians, especially with the detailed publication of the well-grounded work by the Ukrainian Academy of Sciences academician M. P. Vasylenko, titled “How the Lithuanian Statute was Abolished” (1926). This work explores the history of the abolition of the Statute on Ukrainian lands at the beginning of the 19th century (1840) and highlights the decisive role of Kyiv's military governor D. H. Bibikov in this process. The author's approach to emphasizing the significance of the Lithuanian Statute in the development of the Ukrainian territories on the Right and Left Banks is insightful. Ukrainian historian, orientalist, and one of the founders of the Ukrainian Academy of Sciences, Ahatanhel Krymskyi, contributed to the publication. Notably, the research features a thorough source base, including works by prominent Ukrainian and international historians of the 19th century – D. M. Bantysh-Kamenskyi, O. F. Kistiakivskyi, O. Lazarevskyi, B. E. Nolde, I. V. Telychenko (Vasylenko, 1926). (Figure 7).

Fig. 7.

The next group in the collection is a Ternopil publication by 19th-century historians V. Antonovych and D. Ilovaiskyi about the history of the Grand Duchy of Lithuania, and the

Riga multi-volume work "History of Livonia from Ancient Times" by the writer and the editor-publisher Ye. V. Cheshykhin. Full bibliographic details appear on the cover and title page of this rare work by Antonovych and Ilovayskyi. The publication was part of the series "Russian Historical Library," published in 1887 and edited by the notable Ukrainian public and political figure O. H. Barvinskyi. Volume VI covers the history of the Grand Duchy of Lithuania from its early days up to the fall of the appanage system in the 14th century. The auxiliary search engine features separate alphabetical and geographical indexes titled "Alphabetical Index." The Yosyp Pavlovskyi printing house in Ternopil carefully designed the cover, which is decorated with Ukrainian ornamentation. The book is dedicated to the renowned 19th-century Ukrainian Greek Catholic priest, a founding member of the T. Shevchenko Scientific Society and Prosvita (Education) in Lviv, a public figure, and arts patron who actively promoted the development of national culture in Galicia: "To the Most Reverend Father Stefan Kachala in proof of high respect," from the publisher. An interesting fact is that the works of these authors were popular and sought after in Katerynoslav (Dnipro) libraries during the second half of the 19th and early 20th centuries and remained in demand among the educated (Antonovych & Ilovaiskyi, 1887). (Figure 8).

Fig. 8.

In our view, the publication "Belarus and Lithuania" (1890) is valuable for scientists mainly because of the chromolithography of the Cross of 1161 and its 99 engravings of icons, portraits of clergy members, and historical figures from secular and religious architecture of the 19th century. With the help of the appendix – a colour map of the Vilnius and Kaunas provinces of Lithuania – readers can visualize the geographical locations of cities and villages from that historical period. This publication completes a series of books on the history of Western Rus, aimed at the residents of this region, and is devoted to the church, military, and political history of Lithuania up to the 19th century.

A separate book was the master's thesis of the jurist S. O. Bershadskyi, titled "Lithuanian Jews, the history of their legal and social position from Vytautas to the Union of Lublin, 1388–1569" (1883). While studying at Novorosiisk University and living in Odesa, S. O. Bershadskyi decided to focus his scholarly work on understanding the so-called "Jewish question." His comprehensive scientific publication, which he compiled over four years by examining sources

from the Kyiv and Vilno (Vilnius) archives and the Lithuanian Metrica, is devoted to the history and social status of Lithuania's Jews. The book discusses the early period of Jewish consolidation in Lithuania and clarifies its development reasons. Notably, his maternal great-grandfather bore the surname Kovalevskiy and was a kuren Zaporizhzhian otaman at the end of the 18th century. The author maintained close ties with members of the T. Shevchenko Scientific Society, particularly D. I. Yavornytskyi and M. S. Hrushevskiy. The book is dedicated: "To Father and Mother with love and gratitude from the author." The seal on the book indicates that its history is connected with P. I. Kahan, the founder and owner of the Private Men's Jewish Gymnasium, which was evacuated from Vilno to Katerynoslav in 1915. The work's thoroughness is reflected in its six chapters and volume of 431 pages. Its references and explanations are deep, meaningful, and extensive (Andreevskii, 1892). (Figure 9).

Fig. 9.

Researchers are particularly interested in the department of foreign literature, which is part of the university's scientific library. Among its publications, it is worth noting the book by the well-known Finnish history professor at the University of Helsinki, Matti Klinge, "The World of the Baltics" (1995). This book offers the first comprehensive historical overview of the Baltic region, its countries, and peoples, dating from the 11th century to the end of the 20th century, and includes vivid illustrations to accompany the text.

An interesting fact is that some copies from the researched book collection bear seals indicating their affiliation with libraries of Katerynoslav (Dnipro) educational institutions from the 19th to early 20th centuries, as well as private individuals. Notable among them are the "Library of the Katerynoslav Institute of Public Education" (KIPE, DINO), seals by P. Kahan, and the "Main Library of the Ekaterinoslav Non-classical Secondary School." Each copy in the collection has its own history and methods of acquisition, which can be traced through library documents and warrant further investigation.

The link between the Dnipro and Lithuania can be seen in the biography of the renowned botanist and professor at DNU, O. L. Belhard, who was born in Lithuania. He developed an interest in botany at Vilnius Classical Gymnasium, as shown by his handwritten memoirs, now stored in the rare collections of the scientific library. In his memoirs, the scientist fondly remembers the beautiful area near Lentvaris village, 28 km from Vilnius, where he spent his free time: a lake, a local forest, and Count Tyszkiewicz's Gothic castle with a unique English-style park. Childhood memories are vivid, linked to the diverse flora and fauna of the Lithuanian region. In 1914, because of World War I, Alexander Belhard was in Katerynoslav, where he

received higher education and spent 65 years working at O. Honchar Dnipro National University (Scientific Library of Dnipro National University, 1960).

Conclusions

Thus, in modern conditions, researching the world's book heritage remains a relevant and urgent focus of library activities. The book collection on the history, geography, and culture of Lithuania, one of the Baltic countries, provides a solid foundation for studying the origins and historical connections between Ukraine and Lithuania. These rare documents are an important part of high-quality educational programs for higher education students across various specialties. Exploration facilitates an in-depth examination of the country's historical collection to develop a comprehensive understanding of the history and evolution of the book and publishing industry in Ukraine and globally. The collection was examined by types of literature, and the content and focus of scientific, educational, and popular literature were clarified.

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Литва у книжковій колекції університетської книгозбірні

Мета статті полягає в дослідженні книжкової країнознавчої колекції з історії, географії та культури Литви, що зберігається у фондах університетської книгозбірні та класифікована за галузями знань, змістом, авторськими колективами, хронологічними межами, друкарським оформленням. Об'єктом дослідження стали книжкові видання XIX – початку XX ст. з різних відділів наукової бібліотеки. **Методика.** Методологія передбачала вивчення світової та української історичної та літературної спадщини з використанням таких методів дослідження, як аналітико-синтетичний, системно-структурний, порівняльний та статистичний підходи. **Результати.** Результати дослідження свідчать, що дана колекція є ґрунтовним джерелом вивчення країнознавства, зокрема історії Литви та литовського народу з давніх часів до початку XX ст. Колекція бібліотеки виявила цінні за своїм змістом та друкарськими особливостями примірники та допомогла визначити ключові аспекти історичного, географічного й культурного розвитку Литви. Особлива увага приділялася групам авторів та печаткам видавців на виданнях. **Висновки.** У сучасних умовах дослідження світової книжкової спадщини є актуальним і нагальним напрямком бібліотечної діяльності. Колекція, присвячена історії, географії та культурі Литви, дає міцну основу для розуміння витоків та еволюції українсько-литовських відносин. Рідкісні документи є важливою складовою якісного освітнього процесу для здобувачів вищої освіти.

Ключові слова: книжкові колекції XIX–XX ст.; Литва; університетська бібліотека

Received: 29.08.2025

Accepted: 17.12.2025